

PEDAGOGICAL THEORY AND ITS HISTORY

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Abstract. *This article provides information about the processes of change and development of the theory and history of pedagogy. The authors describe the main concepts in the theory and history of pedagogy, as well as their historical origins, and strive to conduct high-quality research in this field. The article analyzes the influence and importance of the ideas and history of pedagogy in the current period. This research opens up new possibilities for teaching and learning by discovering innovations and developments in pedagogy.*

Keywords: *validation, value, education, theory, reasoning, equity, framework, analysis, research.*

The theory of pedagogy is a scientific science in the field of education and upbringing, which studies the processes of human development and improvement of qualifications. Pedagogical theory explores the methodological and psychological foundations of individual teaching and is based on practice in higher education institutions. The history of pedagogy studies the historical processes, educational forms and technologies of scientific-aesthetic cultural development dedicated to people's ability to learn.

Any science has its own research methods. Through these methods, it enriches and updates its content. In life and in the theory of knowledge of the objective world, there are issues of what to teach and how to teach, who should be educated, and they are interrelated. Pedagogy studies existing pedagogical phenomena and processes with the methods that correspond to its goals and tasks in order to enrich and renew its content. The more perfect, reasonable and correctly chosen the research methods of pedagogy are, the better the updating and improvement of educational content will be, and the science of pedagogy will be enriched. Pedagogical skills are the abilities of living people to master and develop students. These skills include learning to work as teachers with flexibility and competence, sharing information with students, and helping them solve problems. Pedagogical skills are essential to educate students by teaching them persistence, patience and enlightenment. Pedagogical communication itself means interaction and relations between educators and teachers. The goal of this dialogue is to help students develop themselves and help them achieve the best possible education. One of the problems that arise when creating new pedagogical methods and ways is the use of communication.

Pedagogical processes include different skills and methods, because each student has his own learning styles and self-techniques. These are studied by teachers, students, parents and scientific researchers and are implemented on the basis of scientific and methodical teachings. Pedagogical processes can include, for example:

1. Methods of students' comprehensive study of information;
2. Methods of formation of educational relations of students;
3. Training and tests on the subject;
4. Formulas and mastering techniques for strengthening students' oppositions.

These processes exist to help students develop their spirituality, experiences and knowledge and are not mutually exclusive. Pedagogy is the theory and practice of education, particularly the methods used in teaching. Technical pedagogy or pedagogical technology refers to the use of technology to enhance the teaching and learning process. It involves integrating educational technology tools and resources to improve learning outcomes.

Pedagogy is a page of scientific, practical and educational responsibility. This word teaches the average pedagogical society, the study of the educational-plane system and program, the determination and formation of goals and general directions, the structure and change of the educational field, and the development of research systems. Pedagogical activities include an important close relationship with teaching. Pedagogical technology, or educational technology, is a word or cocktail system that includes education through the use of technical tools and sites in educational processes. These technologies help to strengthen the educational environment, making the acquisition and distribution of educational information simpler and more efficient. These processes are carried out through the Internet, mobile applications, educational programs, multimedia textbooks and other technological tools. Pedagogical skill is an important practice and method necessary for the development of students' teaching and learning processes. It helps to raise students to the level of scientific knowledge, they strive for creativity in ideological development and social relations. Pedagogical skills provide an overview of new methods and technologies aimed at making teaching more spiritual and practical for students.

The history of pedagogy is the history of theoretical and practical work in the field of education, and it is a method of scientific research related to the study of the educational process, structure and development of a person. The history of pedagogy, the development of thought, understanding and methodical ideas in the field of education, the theoretical and practical foundations of the educational process will occur to students.

Conversation method. This method helps to enrich the information obtained in the process of pedagogical observation, to make a correct assessment of the current situation, to create pedagogical conditions that allow to find a solution to the problem, and to attract the capabilities of subjects of experimental work in solving the problem. Interviews are held individually, in groups, and in a public manner. During the interview, it is important to achieve the full manifestation of the capabilities of the respondents. Questionnaire method (French check). Using this method, evidence collected during pedagogical observation and interview is enriched. The questionnaire method is also based on the organization of communication with the respondents based on structured questions. Answers to questionnaire questions are, in most cases, obtained in writing. The theory and history of pedagogy, pedagogy itself is a knowledge-system of studying education, teaching, learning, training and other educational processes. This field deals with the theoretical and practical foundations of human learning and development. The theory of pedagogy covers the study of the foundations of education and upbringing, the extent to which people can develop themselves in a certain environment, and the study of the main principles of pedagogy. And the history of pedagogy is a scientific direction related to the study of the stages of education and upbringing, the history of their development and important experiences. This field is dedicated to the study and analysis of the historical development of pedagogic ideas and methodological practices. Pedagogy is known as a science in the field of education and upbringing. In this field, psychological and pedagogical foundations of human development processes, educational methods and academic subjects are studied. Pedagogy uses scientific research aimed at developing

people to their best potential. This field has its own special methodology and conceptual models. The rules of students are the main rules in the society that define warm relations between teachers and educators. This position is maintained and its duty is regularly assumed. This rule is valid and separate for the assistant, so it is shown to be safe by the covered educator or teacher and the students to follow it.

The interview method ensures that the respondent reacts to the phenomenon that illuminates one or another aspect of the problem under investigation. Interview is conducted on the basis of referring the series of questions to the attention of the respondent. The reaction of the researcher to the questions received during the interview increases its effectiveness.

Method of analysis of educational institution documents. Information that illuminates the content of the activities of educational institutions in order to verify the pedagogical phenomenon and evidence. This method is a study of the state of implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” and the requirements of the “National Personnel Training Program” in the practice of educational institutions, the level of activity in this regard.

The advantage of this method is characterized by the possibility of analyzing respondents’ answers according to specific criteria and saving time. However, the method is not without some shortcomings. For example, in most cases, the answers are received in writing, as well as the respondent’s offer it is necessary to choose one of the given answer options. Therefore, the respondent does not have the opportunity to express his opinion in detail.

Pedagogical analysis method. From the use of this method in the process of conducting research the intended goal is to determine the level of study of the selected problem in philosophical, psychological and pedagogical directions, and serves to substantiate the theoretical validity of the idea put forward by the researcher.

A method of studying children’s creativity. This method is used to determine the ability, as well as the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications in certain fields of science. Diaries of students’ creative work, essays, written works, abstracts, and reports serve as an important tool for its application. The advantage of the method is that it creates a basis for seeing, evaluating and developing the individual potential of a particular student. In short, pedagogical research methods are teacher’s pedagogy. Improves the accuracy of research tasks aimed at improving the activity, taking into account the age characteristics of students, the laws of child psychology, and increases its level.

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